

Isolation and Molecular Characterization of Bio-Flocculating Bacteria from Afelele River in Offa, Kwara State

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Abstract

The growing demand for safe water in municipal and industrial settings underscores the critical need for effective water treatment methodologies. The environmental and health risks associated with synthetic flocculants commonly used in water treatment processes have been reported thus, the need for safer and more sustainable alternatives to mitigate the drawbacks of synthetic polymers. This study aims to isolate and characterize bacteria with bio-flocculating potential from the Afelele River in Offa, Kwara State. Water samples were randomly collected at different section of the river. The experimental setup involved glucose as the carbon source, CaCl₂ as the cation agent, and kaolin clay to assess the bio-flocculating activity of the isolates. Morphological characteristics were determined while the molecular method confirmed three isolates with significant flocculating activity. Of the 12 isolates with flocculating activities, *Acinetobacter* sp., *Acinetobacter pittii*, and *Providencia rettgeri* had the highest 87.6%, 89.6%, and 81.7%, respectively. Other isolates morphologically identified as *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus* spp, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Corynebacterium* spp and *Enterococcus* spp exhibited varying flocculating activities ranging from 43.4% to 78.3%. Phylogenetic analysis established the significant relatedness of the three isolates to strains deposited in GenBank. The significant flocculating activities of these isolates highlights their potential as bioflocculants for application in water and wastewater treatment.

Keywords: Bio-flocculants, River, Molecular, Water treatment

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Introduction

Wastewater pollutants in natural water bodies are toxic and make water unsafe leading to an upsurge of waterborne diseases. Consumers' demand for safe water makes it imperative for continuous evaluation of water quality and novel treatment protocols that are harmless to the environment and of low cost (Yuli et al., 2023). Also, to ensure proper treatment of effluents before discharge into waterbodies strict rules have been implemented by nations (Afreen et al., 2023).

Flocculation is one of the preferred alternative physicochemical processes for the removal of contaminants and organic materials from wastewater. It groups or clumps together finely distributed particles to create substantial flocs that quickly sediment. The three flocculating agents that have shown significant potential in wastewater treatment are inorganic, organic, and microbial flocculants (Nagavarma et al., 2012). Microbial genera with recorded flocculant production include but are not limited to *Streptomyces*, *Arthrobacter*, *Brachybacterium*, *Cellulomonas* and *Scenedesmus* (Kolawole et al., 2019; Selepe et al., 2024) where the composition was found to include polysaccharides, uronic acids, sugar, and protein amongst others. This can be influenced by a variety of factors, such as the environment, the medium composition in which the microorganisms were cultivated and the bioflocculant's functional groups, morphology, and crystallinity, as well as its pyrolysis profile. However, the exploration of these potential sources of flocculant is still limited. This study therefore aimed to isolate and characterize bio-flocculant-producing bacteria from the Afelele River.

Materials and Methods

Sampling Site Description

Water samples were collected from the Afelele river located at Agun area, Offa, Kwara State, Nigeria which is the most visited river in the area. The coordinates of the sampling site are latitude 8°9'20.0016"N and longitude 4°43'43.9716"E. The river water is a lentic system containing several embankments. The colour of the water is dirty white in appearance and the sediment is muddy black. Several drainage routes from Offa town are directed

toward the river water receiving both point and non-point pollutants with fishing activities also taking place in the river.

Sample collection

The sample was collected from two different points from the Afelele River which include the point of entry, and point of exit of the water. The sample was collected into a sterile container, the temperature was regulated by subjecting the sample to a cool condition using an ice bag for transportation.

Isolation of pure cultures

The respective samples were plated on sterile nutrient agar and then incubated. Sub-culture of distinct colonies was made using streak method into sterile nutrient agar plates. The plates were taped all over to avoid contamination and condensation and then incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Pure cultures obtained were transferred into separate nutrient agar slants in McCartney bottles, and incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours. After observing growth, the agar slants were transferred to a refrigerator as stock cultures (Fawole and Oso, 2004).

Growth media and cultivation conditions for bioflocculant production

The growth medium for bioflocculant production was composed of glucose (10g), MgSO₄·7H₂O (0.3 g), K₂HPO₄ (5 g), peptone (1g), and KH₂PO₄ (2 g) in a litre of distilled water at pH 7 and sterilized by autoclaving (Kolawole et al., 2019). The culture was incubated at 25°C in a shaker at 120 rpm for 7 days and centrifuged at 4000 × g for 30 min at 4°C to sediment the cells. Flocculating activity (FA) was determined using 2 ml of the cell-free culture supernatant.

Production of bioflocculant

Five (5) ml sterile growth medium contained in McCartney bottles and incubated for seven days in a rotary shaker at 25°C, 120 r/min. The fermentation broths obtained were centrifuged at 4000 g for 30 min at 4°C to separate the cells. The cell-free supernatants (liquid), which is the bioflocculant, were used to assay for flocculating activity.

Determination of flocculating activity

Kaolin clay (Sigma-Aldrich natural kaolinite, Al₂O₃·2SiO₂·2H₂O) was used as the test material to model wastewater particles and the flocculating activity of the bioflocculants was determined. A concentration (4 g/L) of kaolin suspension was made. Kaolin suspension

(100mL) was measured into a 250 mL flask with 3 mL of 1% CaCl₂ and 2 mL culture supernatant. After vigorous agitation of the mixture for 60 seconds, it was poured into a measuring cylinder (100 mL) and allowed to sediment at room temperature (5 min) before optical density (OD) measurement of the clarified supernatant at 550 nm. Similarly, a control was prepared but the bioflocculant was replaced with distilled water.

The flocculating activity was calculated with the following formula:

$$\text{Flocculating activity (\%)} = [(A - B)/A] \times 100$$

A = Optical density at 550nm (OD550) of the control.

B = Optical density at 550nm (OD550) of a sample.

The multiple-microorganism consortia of cell-free supernatant that showed high flocculating activity were selected for further studies.

Molecular Identification of Isolates

The molecular protocol utilized the 16S primers (16SF: GTGCCAGCAGCCGCGCTAA; 16SR: AGACCCGGGAACGTATTTCAC) (Kolawole et al., 2019). The product was purified and sequenced to determine the respective species of the organisms. The sequence analysis after blast search at the NCBI was analyzed using the MEGA 11 software package. Sequence trimming, alignment, phylogenetic relatedness, and pairwise distance were also conducted for the sequence (Tamura et al., 2021).

Analysis of Result

Data was collated, manually checked for error, and presented using Microsoft Excel and Word packages. Relevant tables and figures with standard error bars were generated for the respective results. Mega 11 software package was used for sequence analysis.

Results

This section presents the results obtained from the research that was carried out on the water sample from the Afelele River.

Total Bacterial Count of Isolates from Afelele River

The total bacterial count of the isolates represented in Table 1 shows that the highest bacteria count is 2.0×10^7 CFU/mL at the point of exit while the lowest (3.2×10^5 CFU/mL) was at the point of entry.

Morphological Characteristics of Isolates from Point of Entry (Pe1) And Point of Exit (Pe)

Twelve (12) bacteria were isolated from the two sampling locations. The outcome of the microbiological characteristics was used to determine the probable organism (Tables 2 and 3).

Flocculating Activity of Isolates from Point of Entry and Point of Exit

The chart in Figures 1 and 2 illustrates the flocculating activity of the isolated organisms. From the point of entry location, isolate 1,2,5,6, and 7 had above 50% activity out of which isolates 1, 2, and 6 had 87.6%, 89.6%, and 81.7% respectively (Figure 1). At the point of exit, five (5) isolates were gotten out of which only isolates A and B had the activity of 54.7% and 78.3% respectively (Figure 2).

Molecular Identification of Isolates

Phylogenetic relatedness of the three (3) isolates with the highest bioflocculating activities are represented in Figure 3. The red-coloured marker corresponds to numbers 1, 5, and 8 in Table 4 which represents the isolates from this study in comparison to other deposited sequences in the GenBank. The sequence blast outcome from NCBI reveals similarity to deposited sequences as presented in the relatedness and divergence pairwise distance tables (Figure 3 and Table 4) respectively.

Table 1: Total Bacterial Count of Isolates from Afelele River

Sample source	Dilution Factor	Number of colonies	CFU/mL
Point of Entry	1:1000 (10^{-3})	60	6.0×10^4
	1:10,000 (10^{-4})	32	3.2×10^4
Point of Exit	1:100,000 (10^{-5})	20	2.0×10^4
	1:1,000,000 (10^{-6})	18	1.8×10^4

NB: WHO= <1000 CFU/mL**Table 2:** Morphological Characteristics of Isolates from Point of Entry

Isolates	Margin	Size	Elevation	Colour on nutrient agar	Gram reaction	Shape	Most Probable Organism
*1	Irregular	Small	Flat	Bright-yellow	Negative	Rod	<i>Acinetobacter specie</i>
*2	Irregular	Large	Flat	Off-white	Positive	Cocci	<i>Acinetobacter Piti</i>
3	Irregular	Large	Flat	Off-white	Negative	Rod	<i>E. coli</i>
4	Irregular	Large	Flat	Creamy	Positive	Bacilli	<i>Bacillus cereus</i>
5	Entire	Large	Flat	Creamy	Negative	Rod	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
*6	Entire	Small	Flat	Creamy	Positive	Rod	<i>Providencia rettgeri</i>
7	Irregular	Large	Raised	Off-white	Positive	Cocci	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>

Depicts isolates that were confirmed using molecular method*Table 3:** Morphological Characteristics of Isolates from Point of Exit

Isolate	Margin	Size	Elevation	Colour on nutrient agar	Gram reaction	Shape	Most Probable Organism
A	Entire	Small	Raised	Creamy	Positive	Rod	<i>Corynebacterium specie</i>
B	Irregular	Large	Raised	Pale-yellow	Negative	Rod	<i>Bacillus specie</i>
C	Irregular	Medium	Flat	Greenish	Negative	Rod	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
D	Entire	Small	Raised	Off-white	Positive	Cocci	<i>Staphylococcus specie</i>
E	Irregular	Large	Flat	Greenish	Positive	Cocci	<i>Enterococcus specie</i>

Fig 1: Flocculating Activity of Isolates from Point of Entry.

KEY: ISOLATE 1: *Acinetobacter spp*; ISOLATE 2: *Acinetobacter pittii*; ISOLATE 3: *E. coli*; ISOLATE 4: *Bacillus cereus*; ISOLATE 5: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; ISOLATE 6: *Providencia rettgeri*; ISOLATE 7: *Staphylococcus aureus*

Fig 2: Flocculating Activity of Isolates from Point of Exit

KEY: ISOLATE A: *Corynebacterium spp*; ISOLATE B: *Bacillus spp*; ISOLATE C: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*; ISOLATE D: *Staphylococcus spp*; ISOLATE E: *Enterococcus spp*.

Fig 3: Evolutionary relationship of Sequences of the bioflocculant producers. (NB: The red-colored dots are sequenced isolates from this study)

Table 4. Estimates of Evolutionary Divergence between Sequences

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1. <i>Acinetobacter pittii</i>								
2. MF462940.1 <i>Acinetobacter soli</i>	0.220							
3. KF928901.1 <i>Acinetobacter sp.</i>	0.216	0.039						
4. MZ947175.1 <i>Acinetobacter sp. Strain HY1485</i>	0.200	0.049	0.053					
5. <i>Providencia rettgeri</i>	0.339	0.191	0.189	0.199				
6. MK934362.1 <i>Acinetobacter oleivorans strain_r303</i>	0.165	0.039	0.036	0.049	0.192			
7. KF887017.1 <i>Acinetobacter sp.</i>	0.163	0.039	0.037	0.048	0.188	0.001		
8. <i>Acinetobacter sp</i>	0.336	0.253	0.245	0.256	0.393	0.219	0.214	

NB: Numbers 1, 5, and 8 represent sequenced isolates from this study

Discussion

The bacterial count analysis from Afelele River reflects significant pollution where the colony forming units per mL were higher than the surface water quality standard of WHO (2017). The trend in microbial population from entry to exit can be attributed to the declining tendency due to a decrease in the amount of organic matter. Furthermore, Adomako et al. (2021) reported that bacteria considerably multiply upstream and downstream. The result from this study where the bacterial count was higher at the point of exit than point of entry could be associated with pollution of the water along the water flow.

This comprehensive dataset of Tables 2 and 3 aided in understanding the tentative microbial diversity of microorganisms in the river contributing valuable insights into potential contaminants and their characteristics. The molecular confirmation of *Acinetobacter*spp indicates the presence of a genus known for its environmental ubiquity (Kulkami et al., 2017). The identification of *E. coli* is significant, as it is a common indicator of faecal contamination (Bello et al., 2023). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is known for its versatility and association with water sources. According to Hlordzi et al. (2020) *Bacillus* species have demonstrated great ability in maintaining water quality. The microbial analysis from this study unveiled a diverse community of bacteria, each exhibiting distinctive characteristics and potential implications for environmental and public health.

*Acinetobacter*spp exhibited a high flocculating activity for glucose as a carbon source at 89.6%. This flocculating activity is higher than the reported activity by Kolawole et al., 2019 which had a flocculating activity of 78.5% (with *Klebsiella* sp) and a similar study by Nontembiso et al., 2011 which had the highest flocculating rate of 74.72% with *Bacillus* spp using sucrose as carbon source. The report for *Bacillus cereus* and *Bacillus* spp flocculating activity in this study varied significantly (43.9% and 78.3%) where the former aligns with the report by Nontembiso et al., 2011 and Maliehe et al. (2019) using a one-time factor assay. This indicates that *B. cereus* has lower flocculating activity against other *Bacillus* species such as *B. subtilis* and *B. salmalava*.

The report of Yadav et al. (2012) using *Acinetobacter* spp also posits the significant capability of organisms to have active bioflocculants. However, the activity of 90% was slightly higher than the one reported in this study (89.6%) despite similar culture conditions. The recorded activity with *Providencia rettgeri* (81.7%) correlates to a report by Oyewole et al. (2023) where the isolate was from earthen river sludge in Minna, Nigeria. The record of 56.2% with *Staphylococcus* spp aligns with a similar study by Oliveira et al. (2018) where 66.7% and 20% activity were recorded using species of *Staphylococcus* spp. The report difference can be ascribed to culture conditions and compositions.

The differences in flocculating activities from this study to other reports can be due to the organism and the culture conditions (Kolawole and Suleiman, 2020). The substantial flocculating activity with *Acinetobacter* spp, *Acinetobacter pittii*, and *Providencia rettgeri* documented in this study illustrates their potential use for wastewater treatment or water purification activity. The sequence alignment also offers insights into the relatedness of the bio-flocculant producers. The slight difference in similarity index between the *Acinetobacter* spp and *A. pittii* could be responsible for the difference in flocculating activities. Likewise, the sequence similarity between *Acinetobacter* spp and *Providencia rettgeri* could have also accounted for the similarity of flocculating activities compared to other species from this study (Madigan et al., 2018). These isolates can be further explored for purified and concentrated bio-flocculant yield towards application in water treatment and combating the associated risk with synthetic chemicals.

CONCLUSION

This study presents a significant pollution level along the river wherein the bacterial count was higher than the WHO standard. Amongst other isolates studied for bioflocculant production and potential usage in water/wastewater treatment, *Acinetobacter* spp, *Acinetobacter pittii*, and *Providencia rettgeri* had significantly higher activity than others. The activity was adduced to the similarity of the isolates which was also affirmed by the sequence similarity index.

Reference

- Adomako, L. A. B., Yirenya-Tawiah, D., Nukpezah, D., Abrahamya, A., Labi, A. K., Grigoryan, R., Ahmed, H., Owusu-Danquah, J., Annang, T. Y. and Banu, R. A. (2021). Reduced bacterial counts from a sewage treatment plant but increased counts and antibiotic resistance in the recipient stream in Accra, Ghana—A cross-sectional study. *Trop. Med. Infect. Dis.* 6(2): 79. <https://doi.org/10.3390/tropicalmed6020079>.
- Afreen, N., Mohammad, Y., Abdul, Q., Yassine, E., Viola, V., Ijaz, M. K., Sana, B. M., Hesam, K., Satbir, S. S., Chander, P., Hsi-Hsien, Y., Hussameldin, I. and Sayed, M. E. (2023). Wastewater treatment: A short assessment on available techniques. *Alex. Eng. J.* 76: 505–516.
- Bello, O. O., Akinpeloye, B. O., Bello, T. K., Oluwafemi, Y. D. and Bamikole, W. O. (2023). Evaluation of the physicochemical properties and bacterial loads of selected rivers in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Iran J. Microbiol.* 15(6): 788–795.
- Fawole, M. O. and Oso, B. A. (2004). Characterization of bacteria: Laboratory manual of microbiology. 4th ed. Ibadan: Spectrum Book Ltd.; 24–33.
- Hlordzi, V., Kuebutornye, F. K., Afriyie, G., Abarike, E. D., Lu, Y., Chi, S. and Anokyewaa, M. A. (2020). The use of Bacillus species in maintenance of water quality in aquaculture: A review. *Aquac. Rep.* 18: 100503.
- Kolawole, O. M., Yahaya, T. D., Lawal, A. R., Okunade, O. A., Famuwagun, O. O., Agboola, S. O., Karunwi, A. E., Tagbo, V., Okedina, Y. S., Adepegba, T. R., Diallo, A. S., Suleiman, M. M., Ogah, I. J., Anibijuwon, I. I. and Adegoke, A. A. (2019). Screening for bio-flocculant producing bacterial strains from Asa River in Ilorin, Kwara State. *Ann. Sci. Technol.* 4(2): 59–67.
- Kolawole, O. M. and Suleiman, M. M. (2020). Flocculation potential of crude bio-flocculants from bacteria isolated in Oyun River, Ilorin, Kwara State. *Arch. Sci. Technol.* 1(1): 26–32.
- Kulkarni, S. S., Madalgi, R., Ajantha, G. S. and Kulkarni, R. D. (2017). Identification of genus Acinetobacter: Standardization of in-house PCR and its comparison with conventional phenotypic methods. *J. Lab. Physicians.* 9(4): 279–282.
- Madigan, M. T., Martinko, J. M., Bender, K. S., Buckley, D. H. and Stahl, D. A. (2018). Brock biology of microorganisms. Pearson.
- Maliehe, T. S., Basson, A. K. and Dlamini, N. G. (2019). Removal of pollutants in mine wastewater by a non-cytotoxic polymeric bioflocculant from *Alcaligenes faecalis* HCB2. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health.* 16: 4001.
- Nagavarma, B. V. N., Yadav, H. K., Ayaz, A. V. L. S., Vasudha, L. S. and Shivakumar, H. G. (2012). Different techniques for preparation of polymeric nanoparticles—a review. *Asian J. Pharm. Clin. Res.* 5(3): 16–23.
- Nontembiso, P., Sekelwa, C., Leonard, M. V. and Anthony, O. I. (2011). Assessment of bioflocculant production by *Bacillus sp. Gilbert*, a marine bacterium isolated from the bottom sediment of Algoa Bay. *Mar. Drugs.* 9(7): 1232–1242.
- Oliveira, W. F., Silva, P. M. S., Silva, R. C. S., Silva, G. M. M., Machado, G., Coelho, L. C. B. B. and Correia, M. T. S. (2018). *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis* infections on implants. *J. Hosp. Infect.* 98: 111–117.
- Oyewole, O. A., Jagaba, A., Abdulhammed, A. A., Yakubu, J. G., Maude, A. M., Abioye, O. P., Adeniyi, O. D. and Egwim, E. C. (2023). Production and characterization of a bioflocculant produced by microorganisms isolated from earthen pond sludge. *Bioresour. Technol. Rep.* 22: 101492.
- Selepe, T. N. and Maliehe, T. S. (2024). Bioflocculation of pollutants in wastewater using flocculant derived from *Providencia huaxiensis* OR794369.1. *BMC Microbiol.* 24: 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12866-023-03144-w>.
- Tamura, K., Stecher, G. and Kumar, S. (2021). MEGA 11: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics

Analysis Version 11. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/molbev/msab120>.

World Health Organization. (2017). WHO guidelines for drinking-water quality. 4th ed. Geneva: World Health Organization. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241549950>.

Yadav, K. K., Mandal, A. K., Sen, I. K., Chakraborti, S., Islam, S. S. and Chakraborty, R. (2012). Flocculating property of extracellular polymeric substances produced by a biofilm-forming bacterium *Acinetobacter junii* BB1A. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 168: 1621–1634.

Yuli, S., Viktor, S. and János, A. (2023). Surface water monitoring systems—The importance of integrating information sources for sustainable watershed management. *IEEE Access.* (99): 1–1.